

ATYPICAL FACIAL PAIN IN FEMALES AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH OXIDATIVE STRESS

Sadaf Durrani^{*1}, Naheed Khattak², Ubaid ur Rahman³, Mudassir Ahmad Khan⁴

1. Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. email address: sadaf.durrani@kmc.edu.pk
2. Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. email address: naheed.khattak@kmc.edu.pk
3. Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. email address: ubaidurrahman@kmc.edu.pk
4. Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. email address: mudasir.ahmad@kmc.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Article History

Received on 08 Nov 2025

Accepted on 28 Nov 2025

Published on 28 Dec 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Naheed Khattak

Abstract

Objective: In this study we have aimed to measure oxidative stress markers including malondialdehyde (MDA), 8-OHdG (8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine,) and anti-oxidant markers including total antioxidant capacity (TAC), glutathione (GSH) and superoxide dismutase (SOD), in females having chronic atypical facial pain. We also tried to find association between oxidative stress and chronic atypical facial pain in females.

Methodology: It was a cross-sectional/ analytical study conducted over a period of six months. We randomly selected female subjects presenting to the out patient's department of the three tertiary care hospitals of Peshawar, Hayatabad Medical Complex (HMC), Khyber Teaching Hospital (KTH) and Lady Reading Hospital (LRH). All female patients with chronic facial pain and trigeminal neuralgia were included in the study. Female subjects with acute facial pain or those having other major illnesses like diabetes mellitus, liver disease, kidney disease, thyroid problem or malignancies were excluded from the study. Fasting blood samples were analyzed for the biochemical parameters including MDA, 8-OHdG, TAC, GSH and SOD. Data was analyzed with SPSS version 21 and expressed as means \pm SD. P value of 0.05 was considered significant.

Results: We found significantly lower TAC (21.01 ± 5.04 vs 33.82 ± 7.83 , $p < 0.001$), GSH (2.47 ± 0.045 vs 9.25 ± 3.29 , $p < 0.001$), SOD (0.145 ± 0.095 vs 0.55 ± 0.015 , $p < 0.001$) and higher oxidative damage markers MDA (6.65 ± 0.065 vs 2.20 ± 0.956 , $p < 0.001$) and 8- OHdG (3.5 ± 1.4 vs 1.2 ± 0.9 , $p < 0.001$)

Conclusion: Based on the results obtained, atypical facial pain in females have significant association with oxidative stress. Lowering oxidative stress in these patients may help to reduce the intensity and frequency of pain in these patients.

Key Words: Atypical Facial Pain, Oxidative Stress, Malondialdehyde, Anti-oxidant Capacity, Glutathione, Superoxide Dismutase

INTRODUCTION

Atypical facial pain (AFP) is a chronic condition characterized by painful episodes for most of the day not including the diagnostic features of cranial nerve neuralgias or other any other disorders (1). Atypical facial pain is prevalent in females with affecting females more than males, with a female to male ratio as high as 3:1 to 5:1 (2). The less known and yet poorly understood pathophysiology of this condition has been recently associated with central sensitization and oxidative stress (3).

Oxidative stress occurs due to an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation in the body and the its ability to destroy these ROS with the natural anti-oxidant defense systems. Increased production of ROS damages the cell membrane lipid bilayer through lipid peroxidation, cellular proteins and DNA, measured as malondialdehyde, 8-hydroxy-2'deoxyguanosine respectively (4). The body's natural anti-defense mechanisms include enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and a molecule called glutathione (GSH) as well as total anti-oxidant capacity (TAC) (5).

Emerging and latest scientific evidences link oxidative stress to various chronic health conditions including chronic painful conditions, such as fibromyalgia, neuropathies and migraine pains (6). The association of oxidative stress with female atypical facial pain (AFP) is still not fully explored. This gap has

led to the present study which aimed to measure oxidative stress markers and anti-oxidant markers in female patients having chronic atypical facial pain.

Material and Methods

Study Design

This was a cross-sectional/ analytical study conducted over a period of six months at the three tertiary care hospitals of Peshawar; namely HMC, KTH and LRH respectively. The study population consisted of 60 participants. Group A consisted of randomly selected 30 female cases presenting to the OPD with complaints of atypical facial pain including trigeminal neuralgias (TN). We also selected 30 age-matched healthy control females. The cases with diagnosed causes of facial pain were excluded from the study. The control group was randomly selected with no history of chronic pain or any other major illness. All the participants were informed about the study objectives and well informed consent was obtained from them. Approval of the study was obtained from the institutional committee of the Khyber Medical College.

Biochemical Analysis

We collected 5 mL of fasting blood samples from each participant after aseptic condition. A clear serum was collected by centrifuging the samples at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes. The sera were properly labelled and stored at - 80 °C till further analysis. Malondialdehyde (MDA),

Antioxidant Capacity (TAC), Glutathione (GSH), Superoxide dismutase (SOD) and 8-hydroxy de Guanosine (8-OH-dG) were determined using enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method.

Statistical Analysis

Results

Table 1 shows the demographic and biochemical variables of group A 30 females as cases and Group B 30 females as control. The mean age of cases was recorded as 44.6 ±13.4 years and controls as 42. 8 ±12.6 years. In the table it can be seen that the cases have significantly higher values of oxidative stress markers: MDA (6.65 ± 0.065 vs 2.20 ± 0.956, p=<0.001) and 8-OH-dG (3.5±1.4 vs 1.2±0.9,

All data was analyzed with SPSS version 21. The results were expressed as means ± standard deviation (SD). The comparisons of variables between the two groups were done with independent student's t test. P value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

p=<0.001) while they exhibit significantly lower anti-oxidant markers including SOD (0.145 ± 0.095 vs 0.55 ± 0.015, p=<0.001), GSH (2.47 ± 0.045 vs 9.25 ± 3.29, p=<0.001) and TAC (21.01±5.04 vs 33.82±7.83, p=<0.001). These results clearly signify that patients with chronic atypical facial pain had an imbalance between reactive oxygen species production and their scavenging mechanisms leading the patients towards oxidative stress.

Table 1: Comparison of biochemical parameters between the study groups

Variables	Group A Cases n=30	Group B Control n=30	P value
Age (years)	44.6 ±13.4	42. 8 ±12.6	0.594
MDA (nmol/mL)	6.65 ± 0.065	2.20 ± 0.956	< 0.001
8-OH-dG (ng/mL)	3.5±1.4	1.2±0.9	< 0.001
SOD (U/mL)	0.145 ± 0.095	0.55 ± 0.015	< 0.001
GSH (µmol/L)	2.47 ± 0.045	9.25 ± 3.29	< 0.001
TAC ((U/mL)	21.01±5.04	33.82±7.83	< 0.001

Discussion

In the present study cases showed markedly raised levels of oxidative stress markers namely; MDA and 8-OH-dG and severely lower levels of antioxidant processes indicated by low TAC and GSH. Thus, this study demonstrates a significant association of atypical facial pain with oxidative stress. The markedly increased level of MDA in our cases, suggests increased lipid peroxidation. This finding is similar to other studies such as Smathers et al. (2011) observed highly raised MDA levels in reported elevated MDA in neuropathic pain (7). Cell membrane lipid bilayer is disrupted by lipid peroxidation generating reactive aldehydes which further activates pain-signaling pathways which mediate inflammatory and neuropathic pain (8). Our findings suggest that this phenomenon may be particularly pronounced

in trigeminal-mediated pain conditions causing activation of Transient Receptor Potential Ankyrin 1 (TRPA1) pain channels, which are abundantly expressed on trigeminal nociceptors (9). Our study is the first to demonstrate raised 8-OH-dG in chronic pain condition. It signifies DNA damage which may trigger cellular senescence and neuroinflammation, contributing to pain chronicity (10,11).

There is significant decrease of GSH in our study. Glutathione is an abundant endogenous antioxidant responsible for destruction of ROS and regeneration of antioxidants, like vitamin C and vitamin E (12). The depletion of glutathione results in increased hyperexcitability of neurons in the trigeminal nerve system (13). Animal studies have demonstrated potentiated nociceptive

responses to painful stimuli such as capsaicin in glutathione depleted models (14). This study also observed highly decreased superoxide dismutase levels in cases having chronic atypical facial pain. The reduced SOD activity leads to decreased enzymatic destruction of superoxide radicals leading to accumulation of hydrogen peroxide and peroxynitrite (15). Reduced superoxide dismutase activity has been associated with chronic pain conditions e.g complex regional pain syndrome and postherpetic neuralgia (16). Furthermore, decreased total antioxidant capacity (TAC) in our study shows the cumulative effect of enzymatic as well as non-enzymatic depletion of antioxidant mechanisms in the body. Low TAC make the patients more vulnerable to painful flares triggered by stress and inflammation (17-19). The results obtained in our study are more intense possibly due to the chronic and persistent nature of atypical facial pain and also due to female study population which has a link with estrogen hormone. It may be suggested that oxidative stress may serve as an effective therapeutic target in atypical facial pain. Anti-oxidant therapies such as the use of GSH precursor (N-acetylcysteine), vitamin E & C, alpha lipoic acid and coenzyme Q10 have help reduce pain scores in chronic pain conditions (20-23).

Conclusion

Atypical facial pain in females is significantly associated with oxidative stress i.e elevated lipid peroxidation characterized by high MDA and decreased glutathione. These findings suggest that oxidative stress may have a strong role in the pathophysiology of chronic facial pain. Future interventional studies should explore whether antioxidant therapy reduces pain intensity and frequency in these patients.

Limitation

A relatively smaller sample size may account as a limitation of our study.

Recommendation

Future RCT studies are recommended to evaluate the effect of antioxidant supplementation in patients having chronic atypical facial pain.

Conflict of Interest

None

Funding

None

References

- [1] Robblee J, Smith JH, Ahmad S, Geiser R, Ali A. Redefining status migrainosus: A narrative review. *Headache*. 2026 Mar 27. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 41902388.
- [2] Benoliel R, Eliav E. Chronic idiopathic facial pain. In: Sharav Y, Benoliel R, eds. *Orofacial Pain and Headache*. 2nd ed. Elsevier; 2015:197-216.
- [3] Wen H, Wang H, Zhong J, Liu X, Yang Y, Zhang W et al. mGluR5 promotes oxidative stress and central sensitization in chronic migraine through ERK-mediated phosphorylation of Drp1 to activate mitochondrial fission. *Neuroscience*. 2025;584:166-179. PMID: 4083502.
- [4] Liu CC, Lin JH, Hsu TW, Wang CY, Hsu HS. Inhibition of the 4-hydroxynonenal-regulated JNK/c-Jun pathway improves bleomycin-induced lung fibrosis. *Biomed J*. 2025;e100916. PMID: 41076274.
- [5] Wang Y, Ma R, Zhou J, Tan Z, Li H, Shi H et al. Emerging strategies for enhanced glutathione biosynthesis and its biomedical applications. *J Biotechnol*. 2026;402:45-58. PMID: 41308835.
- [6] Borsook D, Youssef AM, Simons L, Elman I, Eccleston C. The pain and oxidative stress nexus. *Pain*. 2018;159(12):2403-2407.
- [7] Smathers RL, Galligan JJ, Stewart BJ, Petersen DR. Overview of lipid peroxidation products and hepatic protein modification in alcoholic liver disease. *Chem Biol Interact*. 2011;192(1-2):107-112.

- [8] Cordero MD, Díaz-Parrado E, Carrión AM, et al. Oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction in fibromyalgia. *Neuro Endocrinol Lett.* 2010;31(2):169-173.
- [9] Rodrigues P, et al. Advanced oxidation protein products activated TRPA1 in a neuropathic multiple sclerosis model. *Brain.* 2025;awaf306. PMID: 40819275.
- [10] Gao W, et al. Utidelone induces mechanical and cold allodynia in mice via TRPA1 activation. *Mol Pain.* 2025;21:17448069251377633. PMID: 40878369.
- [11] Dhande M, et al. Neurobiology of TRPM channels in pain processing: Current advances and future directions. *Life Sci.* 2026;386:124169. PMID: 41443469.
- [12] Lu SC. Glutathione synthesis. *Biochim Biophys Acta.* 2013;1830(5):3143-3153.
- [13] Kim HY, Park CK, Cho IH, Jung SJ, Kim JS, Oh SB. Differential changes in the expression of voltage-gated potassium channels in the trigeminal ganglion following chronic constriction injury of the infraorbital nerve. *Mol Pain.* 2008;4:62.
- [14] Kimura Y, et al. Glutathione Plays a Significant Role in the Growth, Oxidative Stress Response, and Sporulation. *Curr Microbiol.* 2025;83(1):36. PMID: 41264015.
- [15] Fukai T, Ushio-Fukai M. Superoxide dismutases: role in redox signaling, vascular function, and diseases. *Antioxid Redox Signal.* 2011;15(6):1583-1606.
- [16] Eisenberg E, Shtahl S, Geller R, et al. Serum and salivary oxidative analysis in complex regional pain syndrome. *Pain.* 2010;149(3):564-569.
- [17] Chapple IL. Reactive oxygen species and antioxidants in inflammatory diseases. *J Clin Periodontol.* 1997;24(5):287-296.
- [18] Salvemini D, Little JW, Doyle T, Neumann WL. The role of peroxynitrite in the development of pain. *Neurobiol Pain.* 2017;1:1-6.
- [19] Aoyama K, Watabe M, Nakaki T. Regulation of neuronal glutathione synthesis. *J Pharmacol Sci.* 2008;108(3):227-238.
- [20] Nnah IC, Lee J, Wold EA, et al. Therapeutic potential of N-acetylcysteine in pain disorders. *Antioxidants.* 2021;10(5):761.
- [21] Ziegler D, Hanefeld M, Ruhnau KJ, et al. Treatment of symptomatic diabetic polyneuropathy with the antioxidant alpha-lipoic acid: a 7-month multicenter randomized controlled trial (ALADIN III Study). *Diabetes Care.* 1999;22(8):1296-1301.
- [22] Zollinger PE, Tuinebreijer WE, Breederveld RS, Kreis RW. Can vitamin C prevent complex regional pain syndrome in patients with wrist fractures? A randomized, controlled, multicenter dose-response study. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2007;89(7):1424-1431.
- [23] Cordero MD, Alcocer-Gómez E, de Miguel M, et al. Coenzyme Q10: a novel therapeutic approach for fibromyalgia? *Antioxid Redox Signal.* 2013;18(15):1988-1991.